

Harmful Algae News

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Macroalgal blooms, dystrophy, discolourations and fish kills in a Tyrrhenian lagoon

Fig. 1. Collection of dead fish from an extensive dystrophic event in Orbetello Lagoon, Italy, July 2024

Some coastal lagoons have undergone strong processes of anthropic change with the result that they have been transformed from mesotrophic to eutrophic and, eventually, hypertrophic environments. This, by altering their typically resilient euryhaline and eurythermic biocoenoses, has favoured the dominance of *facies* of opportunistic species, microphytes and macroalgae, with impressive vegetative development [1].

Some of these species decay rapidly with rising summer temperatures, mainly as a result of increased bacterial activity [2].

The high organic load on the sediments triggers anaerobic bacterial processes that first lead to the formation of ammonia and rapidly to sulphate reduction and production of hydrogen sulphide. This last process produces dystrophy, kills the sediment fauna and even the vagile fauna if it does not be-

Fig. 2. Orbetello lagoon with its three sea-lagoon canals (slc), two in the West basin and one in the East basin

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NEW!

Fig. 3. Extensive mat of *Valonia aegagropila* in March in the West basin. The mats consisted of large 'balls' floating on the bottom (benthopleustophytic)

come aware of the toxic gas release on time (Fig. 1). Dystrophy is a degradation phenomenon through which the hypertrophic ecosystem reduces its enormous amount of accumulated energy (organic matter). Afterwards, endemic populations may be re-established, but hypertrophy quickly leads to the sedimentation of new organic deposits, and the cycle restarts [3]. The more eutrophic an ecosystem is, the higher the frequency of dystrophic episodes.

The Orbetello lagoon is a shallow, non-tidal, hypertrophic environment with very low flushing rates. It is located on the Tyrrhenian coast of Italy, (42° 25' – 42° 29' N; 11° 10' – 11° 17' E) and consists of two connected basins, West and East, of 15.25 km² and 10.00 km², respectively. The lagoon has three canals which communicate with the sea, two in the West basin (SLC1; SLC2) and one in the East basin (SLC3) (Fig. 2). To get an idea of the degree of hypertrophy, in May 2024, nutrient concentrations in the water column of the West basin were: 238 µM of N-NO₃, 27 µM of N-NH₄ and 3,23 µM of P-PO₄ [4]. This strong eutrophication supports an impressive growth of Chlorophyta *Chaetomorpha linum* and *Valonia aegagropila*. *C. linum* is a cosmopolitan opportunistic species that produces vegetative blooms in many parts of the world, favoured by nutrient availability, particularly P [5, 6]. This species is very resilient to extreme conditions, being able to survive

even dystrophies, although large mats of the alga decay close to the bottom. *V. aegagropila* (Fig. 3) is a typical Mediterranean lagoon species and thrives in mesotrophic environments. It is among the first macroalgal species in the lagoon to decay under critical summer conditions [2]. This fragility is probably due to poor defense against bacterial activity, which increases with temperature rise, since in laboratory culture, in the absence of sediment, the species tolerates temperatures up to 36°C (Lenzi, unpublished data).

In February 2024, the macroalgal biomass estimates were about 30,000

tonnes in the West basin and 23,000 tonnes in the East Basin (Fig. 4). *C. linum* represented 50% of the total biomass, *V. aegagropila* 30%; the remaining percentage was largely made up of Rhodophyta and 5-7% by the Ochrophyta *Gongolaria barbata*. With the exception of *C. linum*, all these species decay under summer conditions.

In July 2024, following a sudden rise in temperature, much of the macroalgal biomass decayed and sulphate-reducing bacteria gained the upper hand. Extensive areas of milky colouration developed in both the West and the East basins, as a result of the release of H₂S from the sediments and its oxidation to colloidal sulphur as it rose in the water column (Fig. 5). Subsequently, secondary bacterial growth occurred, probably anaerobic sulphur-oxidising purple bacteria, and the process affected most areas of the two lagoons (Fig. 5). Indeed, the waters everywhere remained strongly anoxic with very low redox values.

Figure 6 shows the trends in dissolved oxygen (DO, mg/L), redox (Eh, mV) and temperature (T, °C) values obtained on 24 July from multi-parameter probes. The values slowly evolved for the better in the West basin, with a slight rise during the daytime phases (DO = 3 mg/L; Eh = 160 mV) as a result of photosynthetic activity, and then returned to very low levels during nighttime respiration (DO = 0 mg/L; Eh = -400 mV), while in the East basin the values remained consistently very low

Fig. 4. Distribution of high-density macroalgal mats and estimates of their biomass (*C. linum* 50%, *V. aegagropila* 30%, others 20%) in the Orbetello Lagoon in February 2024

Fig. 5. Sentinel-2 images. Left, July 16, 2024: H₂S development and whitewater formation (colloidal sulphur); Right, July 24, 2024, evolution and spread of the phenomenon, with brown debris masses in suspension, and likely development of anaerobic sulphur-oxidising purple bacteria, on the right.

over 24 hours (DO = 0 mg/L; Eh = -400 mV). Temperatures varied between 29°C and 32°C.

The die-off affected all bottom populations including vagile species, and more than 70 tonnes of fish (above all grey mullet, sea-bream and sea-bass) were collected (Fig. 1). Smaller fish were not harvested as at 32°C, they decomposed quickly and sank. This dys-

trophy has resulted in severe damage to the lagoon fishery and the economy of Orbetello city. Significant damage was caused to the tourist industry due to the discoloration of the lagoon waters that flowed into the sea, preventing bathing along the beaches, and because of a putrid smell, caused first by bacterial growth and then by the decomposition of fish. The high and above all persis-

tent temperature rise, combined with the high load of labile organic matter, is an important cofactor triggering dys-

trophy. The abundance of suspended particulate organic matter was estimated at 3.23 ± 0.70 g/L. Considering that for the West Basin alone (avg depth 1 m), the extent of the phenomenon was approximately 930 ha, the suspended organic

Fig. 6. Dissolved oxygen, redox and temperature values obtained from the multi-parameter probes located in the central areas of the two basins. In light blue, the average values for the week preceding the date of 24 July 2024; in blue, the values for the day preceding that date; in red, the values for 24 July. On abscissas, the hours 0 am to 11 pm; on ordinates, mg/L, mV and °C, for dissolved oxygen, redox and temperature, respectively.

Fig. 7. Left, Sentinel-2 image of 5 August 2024. Evolution of the dystrophic phenomenon that occurred in the Orbetello lagoon, with development of Cyanobacteria in the West basin (green water); Right, dissolved oxygen in the central area of the West basin: high values during the daytime, but reaching zero due to intense respiration during night and early morning hours.

matter could have totalled over 30,000 tonnes. This suggests that a significant quantity of debris, able to trigger new dystrophic phenomena, was still available.

The evolution of dystrophic phenomena can take several pathways, much depending on weather and climate conditions:

Pathway 1: Dry winds from the western quadrant favour faster recovery, as they cool the water more rapidly at night, which reduces bacterial activity and favours oxygen uptake. In this case, the water tends to become very dark due to suspended detritus, which is attacked by aerobic bacteria.

Pathway 2: On the contrary, a humid, sea breeze does not promote night-time heat exchange but encourages intense bacterial activity, prolonging anoxia and promoting new dystrophic phenomena.

Pathway 3: Positive evolution of the phenomenon is provided by growth of Cyanobacteria, which produce oxygen and counteract the consequences of dystrophy; this case developed in the West basin in August 2024 (Fig. 7).

The probable secondary development of purple bacteria that occurred in July 2024 in the Orbetello lagoon has yet to be confirmed; it would be a record for the area on the basis of its extent.

- 64(12): 2699-2707. doi: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2012.10.004
4. Lenzi M et al 2024. *J Aquat Mar Biol* 13(2):71-78
 5. Gavio B & JE Mancera-Pineda 2015. *Acta Biologica Colombiana* 20 (2): 259-262
 6. Zhang X et al 2014. *Mar Pollut Bull* 89 (1-2): 229-238

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Harmful Algae in the Egyptian Waters

The author of this guidebook, Prof Amany Ismael, is the current Chair of the IOC Regional Group HANA (Harmful Algae in North Africa).

The book can be freely downloaded from the IOC website: <https://oceanexpert.org/document/34750>

References

1. Smetacek V & A. Zingone 2013. *Nature* 504: 84-88
2. Sorce C et al 2017. *Mar Pollut Bull* 129(2): 772-781 doi: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.10.071
3. Lenzi M et al 2012. *Mar Pollut Bull*

HARRNESS: An Updated Roadmap for HABs in the US

“HARRNESS 2024–2034: Harmful Algal Research and Response, A National Environmental Science Strategy” [1] has been released through the US National Office for Harmful Algal Blooms at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (Woods Hole, Massachusetts, USA). This national strategy builds on major accomplishments from past efforts, provides a state of the science update since the previous decadal HARRNESS plan (2005–2015) [2], identifies key information gaps, and presents forward-thinking solutions to advance research, monitoring, and management of HABs in the US.

Major achievements on many fronts since the last HARRNESS are detailed in this report. They include improved understanding of bloom dynamics of large-scale regional HABs such as those of *Pseudo-nitzschia* on the west coast, *Alexandrium* on the east coast, *Karenia brevis* on the west Florida shelf, and *Microcystis* in Lake Erie. The report highlights advances in HAB sensor technology, allowing deployment on fixed and mobile platforms for long-term, continuous, remote HAB cell and toxin observations. Emerging HABs or impacts are also described.

Many other issues are also highlighted. For example, freshwater HABs now occur in many inland waterways and their public health impacts through drinking and recreational water contamination have been characterized and new monitoring efforts initiated. Furthermore, freshwater HAB toxins are finding their way into marine environments (sometimes termed the “freshwater-to-marine continuum”) and contaminating seafood with unknown consequences. After many years with little or no issues with *Dinophysis* and diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP events), blooms have been documented at multiple locations along the US coast, but the causes of this apparent expansion are not understood. Similarly, blooms of fish- and shellfish-killing HABs are occurring in many regions and are especially threatening to aquaculture.

The science, management, and decision-making necessary to manage the threat of US HABs continue to involve a multidisciplinary group of scientists, managers, and agencies at multiple levels. The initial HARRNESS framework (2005–2015) and the National HAB Committee (NHC) that was formed at that time have proven effective means to coordinate the academic, management, and stakeholder communities interested in national HAB issues and provide these entities a collective voice through this updated HARRNESS national strategy.

The US Congress and Executive Branch have supported most of the advances achieved under HARRNESS (2005–2015) and continue to make HABs a national priority. Congress has reauthorized the Harmful Algal Bloom and Hypoxia Research and Control Act (HABHRCA) multiple times and continues to authorize the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) to fund and conduct HAB research and response, has given new roles to the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and required an Interagency Working Group on HABHRCA (IWG HABHRCA). These efforts have been instrumental in coordinating HAB responses by federal and state agencies.

The update process leading to HARRNESS 2024–2034 began with discussions via a webinar and follow-on survey for the US HAB community. A 26-member Scientific Steering Committee (diverse in geographical location, expertise and career stage) was assembled and divided into core focus groups to concentrate writing efforts within major HAB programmatic areas: 1) **Observing systems, modeling, and forecasting**; 2) **Detection and ecological impacts**, including genetics and bloom ecology; 3) **HAB management** including prevention, control, and mitigation, and 4) **Human dimensions**, including public health, socioeconomics, outreach, and education. Focus groups were tasked with addressing: a) our current understanding based on advances since HARRNESS 2005–

2015; b) identification of critical information gaps and opportunities; and c) proposed recommendations for the future. Committee members sought input from an additional 35 contributors and reviewers to ensure production of a comprehensive document. Affiliations spanned academia, federal and state agencies, institutions, industry, the non-profit sector, private industry, and tribal organizations.

The aim of this interdisciplinary effort was to provide summary information that will guide federal, state, local and tribal agencies and nations, researchers, industry, and other organizations over the next decade to collectively work to address HAB problems in the United States.

The vision statement for HARRNESS 2024–2034 has been updated, as follows: **“Over the next decade, in the context of global climate change projections, HARRNESS will define the magnitude, scope, and diversity of the HAB problem in US marine, brackish and freshwaters; strengthen coordination among agencies, stakeholders, and partners; advance the development of effective research and management solutions; and build resilience to address the broad range of US HAB problems impacting vulnerable communities and ecosystems.”**

References

1. US National Office for Harmful Algal Blooms, “Harmful Algal Research & Response: A National Environmental Science Strategy (HARRNESS), 2024–2034,” Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, Woods Hole, Massachusetts, 2024, DOI 10.1575/1912/69773
2. HARRNESS, 2005. Harmful Algal Research and Response: A National Environmental Science Strategy 2005–2015. Ramsdell, J.S., D.M. Anderson and P.M. Glibert (Eds.), Ecological Society of America, Washington DC, 96 pp.

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Biotic control of harmful algal bloom formation and toxin production (BIOTOX)

Fig. 1. Top, Mussel rafts in Bueu, the hot spot of DSP events in Galicia; Bottom, Red tide of *Alexandrium minutum* in Campelo, at the head of the ría. Ría de Pontevedra, nW Spain (Photos by Fran Rodríguez) 2018.

BIOTOX (2022-2026) is a new coordinated project funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation. BIOTOX combines expertise in Harmful Algal Blooms and the dinoflagellate culturing capacities of the VGOHAB group (<https://vgohab.com/>) of the Spanish Institute of Oceanography in Vigo with the scientific capacity in microbial plankton interactions and the mesocosm facility of the Biological Oceanography Group (GOB) at the University of Vigo (<http://gobio.webs.uvigo.es/index.php?lang=es>) to explore the role of biotic factors on the development of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in the Galician Rías (NW Spain), using *Alexandrium minutum* as a model system.

HABs may cause significant socio-economic impacts in the Galician Rías, which support intensive aquaculture and fisheries favoured by the prevalence of coastal upwelling conditions from spring to autumn (Figure 1). As a result, high primary productivity and periodical occurrence of algal blooms, including harmful species, are observed in the Rías. The increasing occurrence of harmful microalgae (and associated shellfish harvesting closures) in the Rías Baixas has been linked with the decreasing extension and intensity of the upwelling season in the NW Iberian Peninsula in recent decades [1]. The initiation, duration and intensity of HABs have been related to different biologi-

cal, chemical and physical factors, but the relative impact of abiotic and biotic factors is still poorly understood.

BIOTOX aims to assess how biotic interactions of *Alexandrium minutum* with its bacterial microbiome, parasites and angiosperms affect bloom formation and toxin production, and to tackle outstanding problems in marine microbial ecology. Quantification of the impact of biotic interactions on HAB formation and toxicity, and their regulation by environmental conditions, are essential to improve our understanding of HAB dynamics and toxicity. These ambitious goals require an ample range of biological knowledge and advanced methodological approaches.

BIOTOX formulates four hypotheses: 1) Temporal variations in the composition of the bacterial microbiome influence growth and toxin production of *A. minutum*, 2) The impact of the bacterial microbiome on *A. minutum* bloom development and toxin production is mediated by chemical substances promoting algal growth and/or toxin production, 3) Parasitic infection plays an important role during *A. minutum* bloom development, influencing growth, toxicity, life cycle and genetic variability of the host, and as consequence, the size and duration of the bloom and 4) Bioactive substances derived from *Zostera marina* meadows inhibit growth and toxin production of *A. minutum* and are released into the water column, impacting the microbial community.

To test these hypotheses, a working plan combining field sampling and different experimental approaches was defined.

Intensive sampling at a station in the Galician Rías over a two-year period allows characterization of the microbiomes (bacteria and parasites) associated with blooms of *A. minutum*. Combined 16S and 18S rRNA amplicon sequencing and the use of advanced imaging flow cytometry (IFC) (Cytosense®) characterize the pico-, nano- and micro-phytoplankton components of the community.

Exclusion experiments, where bacterial activity is blocked by adding antibiotics, and transplant experiments, where quasi-axenic *A. minutum* is inoculated on natural bacterial communities collected from these proliferations

Fig. 2. Several products obtained from imaging flow cytometry (CytoSense®). (A) Cytochrome of pico- and nanophytoplankton. Cell concentration data are obtained for RedPicoProk (*Prochlorococcus*), OraPicoProk (*Synechococcus*), RedPico (pico-eukaryotes), RedNano (nano-eukaryotes) and OraNano (nano-cyanobacteria and *Cryptomonas*) plankton components (as defined in Thyssen et al. 2022); (B) Image of *Alexandrium minutum* and (C) associated pulse shape; (D) Submersible mode for in situ sampling of the water column.

provide information about the effect of bacterial microbiomes on the dynamics and toxin production of these blooms. As a complementary tool, the analysis of the bacterial metatranscriptomes derived from field and transplant experiments provides insightful information to unveil molecules potentially driving allelopathic interactions; these will be corroborated using simple bioassay experiments.

The effects of parasites on *A. minutum* growth, life cycle transitions and cellular toxin content are being studied by exposure of *A. minutum* cells to different host-parasite ratios; parasitic exudates from these treatments are tested to evaluate their allelopathic effects. The potential link between life cycle and toxin content will be studied using clonal cultures with no capacity of zygote formation and in sexual populations.

Finally, to evaluate if bioactive substances derived from *Z. marina* meadows released into the water column inhibit *A. minutum* growth and toxin production, microcosm experiments with natural exudates of *Zostera marina* and mesocosm experiments including natural *Zostera marina* beds are ongoing.

Preliminary results

- Samples for imaging flow cytometry (IFC) are analyzed a few hours after collection, avoiding the use of fixa-

tives that usually alter the morphological and physiological properties of the cells (Fig. 2). Micro-phytoplankton cell densities at genus or species level are estimated from the supplementary information provided by pulse shapes of each particle and the collection of acquired images (Figure 2B-C). In addition, the equipment can be submerged at different depths to obtain in situ information on the vertical distribution of phytoplankton assemblages and species related to water column structure (Figure 2D).

- Analyses of the bacterial microbiome of *A. minutum* strains isolated from Ría de Vigo showed a dominance of

Fig. 3. The composition of the bacterial microbiome of *A. minutum* strain V1, isolated from Ría de Vigo is dominated by Flavobacteriales (mostly *Winogradskyella*) and an uncultured *Rodhobacteraceae*.

Flavobacteriales and Rhodobacterales. These groups were previously associated with natural dinoflagellate blooms [2] (Fig. 3). Ongoing DNA metabarcoding of samples collected during the progression of a natural bloom in 2023 will soon provide further insights into the microbiome of *A. minutum* in the field.

- Monitoring data from the fixed sampling location showed that *A. minutum* cell density was directly related to the prevalence of *Parvilucifera sinerae* infections (Fig. 4 A-B), the only dinoflagellate parasite identified at this site. Thirty four clones of *P. sinerae* were isolated to perform infection studies. Infection can be monitored by flow cytometry (Fig. 3C), since it is characterized by a DNA peak to the left of the peak corresponding to the basic DNA content of *A. minutum* (control), whereas peaks to the right of the control indicate dinoflagellate growth. Our preliminary results suggest that at certain parasite:host ratios, *Alexandrium* toxin quota (GTX3 content per cell) may increase in some strains (Fig. 4 D-E) and that this infectious process depends on the host susceptibility.
- Increasing exudate concentrations from unaltered *Z. marina* leaves during 24 h significantly reduced *A. minutum* growth rate even at the

Fig. 4. *Parvilucifera infectans* Infection stages (A-B) after DNA staining with sytox green. Fully infected cell of *A. minutum* (A) and its parasite free stage (B). (C) Flow cytometry histogram showing DNA content peaks for controls (uninfected and synchronized dinoflagellate cultures) and for infected and uninfected growing cultures. Toxin content per cell (GTX3) of *Alexandrium* cells from different clones (1:1, host:parasite ratio) in infected (D) and uninfected (control) cultures (E). Sampling 1 and 2 indicate replicate experiments.

lowest concentration in preliminary microcosm experiments (Fig. 5). The highest concentration tested prevented any increase in dinoflagellate numbers throughout the experiment. Parallel cultures treated with antibiotics led to the conclusion that the growth rate decline was a direct effect of substances released by *Z. marina* or its attached microbiome and not an indirect effect medi-

ated by the stimulation of coexisting bacteria [3]. New experiments have been designed: i) to assess whether the observed inhibitory effect varies seasonally and with the tide level, and ii) to elucidate whether *Zostera marina*'s microbiome has a role on the negative interactions between seagrass meadows and dinoflagellates. Further stage investigation plans include: 1) identification of the

Fig. 5. Changes in abundance of *A. minutum* exposed to different concentrations (0, low, medium and high) of the substances released by unaltered *Z. marina* leaves during a 24 h incubation.

bioactive molecules potentially responsible for the dinoflagellate response and 2) In depth assessment of the morphological and metabolic changes on *A. minutum* cells induced by the allelopathic compounds

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References

1. Álvarez-Salgado XA et al 2008. *Harmful Algae* 7(6), 849-855
2. Hattenrath-Lehmann TK & C J Gobler 2017. *Harmful Algae* 68, 17-30
3. Díaz-Alonso A et al 2024. *Harmful Algae* 133, 102605
4. Thyssen M et al 2022. *Front Mar Sci* 9, 1-13

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Introducing Citizens of the Sea!

We are officially launching this new charity in May this year to harness the range and capability of offshore cruisers and ocean racers to collect ocean biodiversity data at scale. Citizens of the Sea (Fig. 1) will be equipping fleets of vessels to collect eDNA, photogrammetric and environmental data as they race across oceans and cruise between Pacific Islands in the coming months.

One key innovation is the **TorpeDNA** (Fig. 2), a ground-breaking plankton net device designed to collect environmental DNA (eDNA) from sea surface water samples while towing the device behind a boat for only 5 minutes. Its innovative

features include affordability, compact size, and enhanced usability, facilitated by a streamlined torpedo design that enables operation at up to 12 knots speed. The simple protocol avoids contamination and allows users to isolate eDNA samples rapidly and with minimal hands-on time. The samples are then sent to the Cawthron Institute for swift metabarcoding analyses of bacteria, plants and animals detected in the samples. With enough spatio-temporal coverage, this approach can help measure ocean health, detect rare or endangered species, and more effectively monitor HABs and other pathogens.

With climate change threatening marine ecosystems, monitoring biodiversity and the spread of harmful algae is an urgent and important task. In collaboration with sailors, scientists, and local communities we can revolutionise how data is collected in the ocean, to benefit marine management, biosecurity, and climate science.

Learn more at: <https://www.citizensofthesea.org>

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Fig. 1. Citizens of the Sea, launch May 2024.

Insights from an ad hoc International Workshop on Dinoflagellate Cysts in Vigo (Spain)

Fig. 1. Participants in the International WS on Dinoflagellate cysts by the hall of the Redeiras building in Vigo, Spain

Between June 18th and 21st, 2024, an International Workshop on Dinoflagellate Cysts was held in Vigo (Galicia, Spain). This event, hosted by the Marine Research Centre (University of Vigo) brought together 27 scientists from 13 countries, including Belgium, Camerouns, Canada, China, France, Germany, Greece, Mexico, Norway, Portugal, Spain, UK, and USA (Fig. 1).

Participants were primarily biologists and geologists with specialized training in various fields such as microscopy, genetics, biogeochemistry, computer science, taxonomy, and more, but they all shared a common denominator on using **dinoflagellate cysts as a research tool**. The major goals of the workshop were to facilitate discussions on cutting-edge research, improve methodological approaches, and explore new collaborative opportunities related to the field of dinoflagellate cyst research.

Cysts are resistant stages in the life-cycles of many dinoflagellates which among other functions are involved in the survival and dispersal of the species. Some taxa are potentially toxic harmful algal bloom (HAB) forming species, such as *Alexandrium* spp., *Gymnodinium catenatum*, *Gonyaulax spinifera* complex, *Lingulaulax polyedra* (syn. *Lingulodinium polyedra*), *Pyrodinium*

bahamense and *Protoceratium reticulatum* (Fig. 2). After being produced in the upper water column, their cysts sink to the ocean floor where some species can remain viable for more than a hundred years.

Dinoflagellate cysts have great geological preservation potential and have

left fossil records from earlier times. This gives us the opportunity to study this group of organisms from both perspectives: biology and geology. In the workshop, the participants shared their latest findings and techniques and discussed cyst applications in various disciplines, such as modern and past (late Quaternary) biology and ecology. **Barrie Dale**, Emeritus Professor at the University of Oslo (Norway) highlighted the importance of integrating both perspectives (living and geological) to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of dinoflagellate ecology and their response to environmental changes.

The four-day workshop was held in the Redeiras building, a traditional fishermen's house recently restored for scientific and cultural events. It is located in O Berbés, an emblematic neighbourhood in the historic centre of Vigo, and offers beautiful views of the ría. The setting chosen for this event was very pertinent, since Ría de Vigo is known for its high primary productivity and marine biodiversity. This coastal inlet, site of the largest fishing port in Europe, has been a major source of food for the local population and, today, along with the other Galician rias, is a leading area of world importance for aquaculture and seafood production. Red tides

Fig. 2. Cysts of potentially toxic HAB-forming dinoflagellates a) Cyst of *Alexandrium* sp. from the Chukchi Sea (taken by Vera Pospelova); b) Cyst of *Gonyaulax spinifera* complex (cyst equivalent *Spiniferites mirabilis*) from sediments off Portugal [1]; c) Cyst of *Lingulaulax polyedra* (cyst equivalent *Lingulodinium machaerophorum*) from sediment off Portugal; d) Cyst of *Protoceratium reticulatum* (cyst equivalent *Operculodinium centrocarpum sensu* [2] from sediments off Cape Blanc, NW Africa ([3]; e) Cyst of *Gymnodinium catenatum* from sediments of the Ría de Vigo, NW Iberia [4]; f) Cyst of *Gonyaulax* sp. (cyst equivalent *Impagidinium aculeatum*) from water samples off Cape Blanc NW Africa [3] Scale bars = 10 µm.

Fig. 3. Daniel Rey García, Director of the host institution (CIM), greets the participants.

and HABs caused by dinoflagellates and other microalgae have been a recurrent phenomenon in the rias for many years, and are the focus of extensive research, including studies conducted by **Iria García-Moreiras** (CIM-University of Vigo, Spain), and by María Portela and Beatriz Reguera (VGOHAB Group, IEO-CSIC), who actively participated in the workshop discussions.

Daniel Rey García, director of the hosting institution (CIM), welcomed the participants and stated that the event provided an excellent platform for scientists to share their knowledge, experiences, and perspectives (Fig. 3). He highlighted the importance of continued research on dinoflagellate cysts to better understand marine ecosystems and climate change. The workshop started with an icebreaking session where participants introduced themselves and their research directions. The program included interactive oral presentations, hands-on laboratory sessions and a field trip. A total of 18 oral presentations were followed by enthusiastic discussions on various aspects of dinoflagellate cysts. These included the use of AI in palynology, palaeoecological signals and preservation of cyst assemblages, cyst taxonomy and extraction techniques, genetic and organic-geochemical approaches, and their application in studies of past cyst distributions and ecology (late Quaternary studies), as well as in modern biology and ecology (including bloom dynamics and the detection of potentially toxic species).

Robert Williams (Norwegian Offshore Directorate, Norway) underlined

that high-resolution scanners and image processing techniques, which are already commonly used in pathology for the diagnosis of diseases, have the potential to be used for digitalizing microscope slides and automating the analysis of dinoflagellate cyst assemblages. Moreover, he explained how machine learning and AI techniques can assist in interpreting dinoflagellate cyst assemblages and speed up the identification and counting process. Whilst these techniques currently require a high financial investment and are still under development for marine palynology, the participants agreed on their promising future applications in the field of cyst analysis.

Highlights of interest to the HAB

community included the talk by **Vincy Winifred** from the University of Minnesota (US) who, together with her collaborators, observed high numbers of *Alexandrium catenella* cysts in palynologically processed surface samples from the Bering Sea. **Vincent Iratçabal**, from the University of Southern Brittany (France), presented the first results of his research team on dinoflagellate cyst mapping in a coastal area commonly affected by toxic events produced by cyst-forming dinoflagellates, which leave a record in the sediments. **Ana Amorim** (University of Lisbon, Portugal) and **Beatriz Reguera** (IEO-CSIC, Spain) promoted a line of discussion on the need for more dinoflagellate cyst studies to broaden our understanding of their distributions, abundances and diversity and improve our understanding of the HAB dynamics produced by cyst-forming species.

Haifeng Gu, from the Third Institute of Oceanography-MNR (China), presented their latest results on diversity estimates based on metabarcoding data from cysts extracted from surface sediments, and showed that genetics can help to study the biogeography of toxic species, particularly those whose cysts are difficult to identify microscopically (Fig. 4). **Girish Beedessee**, from Northumbria University (UK), showed how high-throughput omics technologies are bringing new insights into the understanding of the functioning of dinoflagellate genomes, and presented a

Fig. 4. Haifeng Gu presented the latest research of his team on metabarcoding in dinoflagellate cysts to study dinoflagellate diversity and harmful algal bloom (HAB) dynamics.

Fig. 5. Pjotr Meyvisch explained what fossilizable biomolecules are and their relevance in the interpretation of fossil dinoflagellate cyst records.

new technique being developed which may help understand the genome biology and secondary metabolism of dinoflagellates and their response to environmental stresses. **Jan Janouskovec**, from the University of Southampton (UK), remarked that interdisciplinary collaboration is important to resolve the phylogenetic tree of dinoflagellates (Fig. 5). The use of multigene phylogenies is helping resolve dinoflagellate relationships but there is still the need for more data on groups well represented in the fossil records and from extant families of uncertain affinity. **Pjotr Meyvisch** (Ghent University, Belgium) gave an insightful talk on the chemical composition of the cyst wall (studied by infrared spectroscopy) and how it supports the assessment of the ecology, preservation and fossil history of dinoflagellate cysts (Fig. 5).

During the session on palaeoceanography, we learnt more about the detection of (palaeo)environmental signals from dinoflagellate cyst assemblages. For instance, **Anne de Vernal** (Geotop–University of Quebec in Montreal, Canada) proposed *Nematosphaeropsis labyrinthus* as a new tracer of the upper mixed layer depth. **Amy Dale** (GeoResearch Consulting, Norway) and **Eldo Roza** (MARUM–University of Bremen, Germany), showed their sediment trap research and explained how such studies provide valuable insights into the production, transport, preservation, and accumulation of cysts in offshore

marine environments, which can help to interpret the sediment cyst signals and obtain more accurate palaeoenvironmental reconstructions from sedimentary records. Several researchers presented their latest reconstructions of past marine environments from down-core cyst records. These included **Fang Gu**, affiliated to the University of Göttingen (Germany) and the University of Geoscience (China), who presented a reconstruction of the last 16 thousand years in the Brazil-Malvinas Confluence, and **Eugenia Fatourou**, from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (Greece), of the last 1.1 mil-

lion years in the Gulf of Corinth (North-east Mediterranean). Furthermore, we learned from the presentation by **Karin Zonneveld** (MARUM–University of Bremen, Germany) how dinoflagellate cyst assemblages from coastal sediments enable reconstructions of past climate changes and their relationship to the early pandemics in Europe during Roman times. Finally, **Javier Helenes**, from the CICESE Institute in Mexico, remarked that comparing older fossil cyst records with more recent ones is very useful for the interpretation of past environmental signals from sediment cyst assemblages and can help evaluate future scenarios.

During the microscope session at the Botany Laboratory on the University de Vigo Campus (Fig. 6), participants compared dinoflagellate cyst morphotypes from different regions of the world. Various aspects related to sample storage, laboratory processing, identification, and cyst nomenclature were also covered in the laboratory and discussion sessions. **Vera Pospelova** (University of Minnesota, US) and **Kenneth Mertens** (IFREMER, Concarneau, France) led the discussions and made detailed presentations on cyst extraction techniques and new developments regarding cyst taxonomy and nomenclature.

A field trip was organised to the Cies Islands, a unique natural area and part of the Atlantic Islands National Park (UNESCO natural heritage candidate). During a tguided tour of the central is-

Fig. 6. The workshop participants during the laboratory session in the Botany Laboratory on the University of Vigo campus.

Fig. 7. Participants in the tour pose by the “Pedra da Campá” (Bell Stone) in the Cíes Islands National Park.

land (Isla del Faro) (Fig. 7), participants learned about the biodiversity and ecological importance of the National Park, the geomorphology of the area, the dynamics of seabirds and other local fauna, and ongoing projects to remove invasive species. Participants were impressed by the stunning views, unique geological formations, and the high number of breeding yellow-legged gulls with their newborn chicks.

The final round table provided a summary of the key topics discussed during the previous days. It also aimed to identify needs and challenges, and to outline future strategies. B. Reguera pointed to the fact that palynologists are applying a dichotomous classification of cyst formers into autotrophs and heterotrophs, often ignoring the capacity of mixotrophic behaviour in most dino-

flagellates [5]. The word “mixotrophy” appeared in the title of only one presentation. Several scientists emphasized the importance of merging data from various fields to enhance biogeographic studies and gain a better understanding of the variability in past and present dinoflagellate communities.

Regarding future directions, it was suggested that standard protocols for sample collection, processing and data analysis should be established to ensure data comparability across different regions. Additionally, there is a need to reach a consensus on cyst taxonomy and nomenclature. It was also highlighted that the development of molecular techniques, such as metabarcoding, is a priority for future research to complement traditional morphology-based identification methods in present-day

and past studies on dinoflagellate distribution and ecology. An effort should also be made to implement the use of sediment traps in cyst dynamics’ studies, which will immensely help interpret paleoecological signals. Given that cyst-forming dinoflagellate are extremely sensitive to environmental changes, excystment and encystment dynamics provide valuable tools to monitor the effects of climate and anthropogenically induced changes in marine ecosystems.

Workshop organisers (Fig. 8) and participants wrote a “white paper” that summarizes the current state of research in dinoflagellate cysts and outlines future directions. Hopefully, this workshop and its resulting publications will demonstrate the importance of dinoflagellate cysts as tools in the study of marine biodiversity, biogeography, HABs, and palaeoceanography, in addition to their use for evolutionary studies and phylogenetics.

References

1. *García-Moreiras I et al 2021. Front Mar Sci 8: 699483. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.699483> Wall D and Dale B 1968. *Micropaleontol* 14: 265-304. doi: 10.2307/1484690*
2. *García-Moreiras I et al 2024. Mar Environ Res 199:106577. doi: 10.1016/j.marenvres.2024.106577*
3. *García-Moreiras I et al 2023. Mar Micropaleontol 180:102217. doi: 10.1016/j.marmicro.2023.102217*
4. *Mitra A et al 2024. J Eukaryot Microbiol e12972. doi: 10.1111/jeu.12972*

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Fig. 8. Members of the international scientific committee. From left to right: Vera Pospelova, Ana Amorim, Iria García-Moreiras (local organiser), Kenneth Mertens and Karin Zonneveld.

Harmful Algal Bloom Impacts on Sustainable Ocean Foods Highlighted at United Nations Event

Fig. 1. The UN Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea supports the implementation of UN Sustainable Development Goal 14 to conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development

Harmful algal blooms were a key discussion topic at the 24th meeting of the United Nations Informal Consultative Process on Oceans and the Law of the Sea (ICP-24) in New York, 17-19 June 2024. The three-day event, led by the UN Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea (Fig. 1) featured individual presentations and panel discussions with UN delegates addressing the ocean as a source of sustainable food. ICP-24 emphasized sustainable ocean foods as an area where coordination and cooperation at the intergovernmental and inter-agency levels should be enhanced, and recognized the impacts of harmful algal blooms (HABs) on the safety and security of sustainable ocean foods.

During this event, Philipp Hess (PHYTOX Director, *IFREMER*) discussed the biological and chemical diversity of HABs in a changing climate and related risks to food safety and security; Maggie Broadwater (*ECO HAB* Program Manager, NOAA/NCCOS) discussed the impacts of HABs on the environment, societies and economies; and Don Anderson (Senior Scientist, *WHOI*) shared technologies and approaches to HAB early warning, mitigation, and control, with a focus on NCCOS-funded research on *Alexandrium catenella* blooms in Alaska and control

technologies for *Karenia brevis* in Florida (Fig. 2).

The *HAB Solutions Programme*, recently endorsed by the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, was highlighted during the presentations. This program is led by the Intergovernmental Panel on HABs (*IP-HAB*), and will augment existing international coordination efforts through the IPHAB, GlobalHAB and IOC Regional Working Groups, and bolster cooperative efforts to reduce the adverse

impacts of HABs on sustainable ocean foods. *HAB Solutions* aims to enhance knowledge and understanding of the causes and effects of HABs at the level of scientists, societal stakeholders, and the public at large, through comprehensive public awareness campaigns, education initiatives, and interdisciplinary solutions that reduce the frequency and severity of HAB events and minimize their adverse effects on the social, economic and natural environments.

Authors

Philipp Hess, *IFREMER*, Nantes, France

Maggie Broadwater, *NOAA*, Charleston, South Carolina, USA

Don Anderson, *WHOI*, Woods Hole, Massachusetts, USA

Fig. 2. Philipp Hess, Maggie Broadwater, and Don Anderson at the UN ICP-24 meeting. Philipp and Maggie currently serve as the Chair and Vice Chair, respectively, of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on HABs (IPHAB), and are working to advance the IPHAB's HAB Solutions Programme

Upcoming events

HAB Session at the International Aquaculture Society Meeting – Aquaculture 2025

A Harmful Algal Blooms session will be organized at the **Aquaculture 2025** meeting, International Aquaculture Society, in New Orleans from March 6-10, 2025 – <https://www.was.org/Meeting/code/AQ2025>

The abstract submission deadline is September 30.

Contact:
Alan Wilson wilson@auburn.edu

2025 Xiamen Symposium on Marine Environmental Sciences

January 14-17, 2025

HAB session at Xiamen Symposium on Marine Environmental Sciences (XMAS) 2025

The Xiamen Symposium on Marine Environmental Sciences (XMAS) was first initiated by State Key Laboratory of Marine Environmental Science, Xiamen University (MEL) in 2014 to promote interdisciplinary studies in marine environmental science. Since then, it has grown to become one of the largest conferences in marine science in Asia.

The upcoming XMAS 2025 will take place in Xiamen, China, from January 14-17, 2025. During this event, a session on Harmful Algal Blooms will be hosted: ***Alleviating the Impact of Emerging Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) to Coastal Ecosystems and Seafood Safety for a Sustainable and Healthy Ocean***

Conveners: Po Teen Lim, Haifeng Gu, Xiaolong Yu, Chui Pin Leaw

This session welcomes studies on emerging HAB events, including research on microalgae and macrophytes harmful events in the Asian Pacific region and beyond. Topics of interest include:

1. Dynamics of HABs, from molecular to ecological aspects, including transboundary events.
2. Knowledge gaps on the physiological and molecular responses of HAB species from tropical to temperate regions.
3. Early warning systems of HABs using novel technologies.
4. Development of monitoring (automated and in-situ) and mitigation (modified clays and other) technologies to minimize the impacts of HABs to mariculture.

5. Trends and emerging HAB events (species, occurrence, and frequency) of regional importance under changing climate conditions.

Presentations related to international collaborations and joint research efforts in addressing the expanding HAB issues in the region are also welcomed.

Details of the session can be found on the XMAS 2025 website: https://xmas.acnf.org/all_session_proposal

Contact:
Prof Chu Pin Leaw, cpleaw@um.edu.my

ISSHA 21st International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA)

The 21st edition of ICHA will be held in Punta Arenas (Magallanes, Chile) from October 19 to 24, 2025

More information

<https://issha.org/icha-conference/> and <https://icha2025.org/>

Important dates

Registration Opens: January 13th 2025
Early Bird ends: May 16th 2025
Late Registration ends: Sept. 19th 2025

Abstract submission

Opens January 20th 2025
Deadline: June 1st 2025

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Deadline to submit material for next issue;
November 1, 2024

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